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1 Introduction

In this report, we take the learnings of all the work performed under LIGHTCAP and translate these into implications and recommendations for design and research. As was shared in the integrative reports on mechanisms and methods, quite some work in the LIGHTCAP project is still ongoing, which necessitates caution when drawing firm conclusions. Still we aim to summarize the most important findings and expectations regarding the research questions that drove the LIGHTCAP project in this report: what have we learned or do we expect to learn in the near future. The project primarily targeted questions around non-image forming effects of light on Cognition, Attention, and Perception (CAP). But our investigations also covered themes beyond CAP, in particular, they encompassed multiple studies related to health and sleep, as well as those on safety. After presenting our key findings, we reflect on how these insights can help us contemplate better light environments, how we can support designers to realize better light environments, and which grand research challenges still lie ahead in the field of lighting research.

2 Summary of major findings

2.1 CAP: Cognition, Attention, Perception

2.1.1 Perception

Several studies in LIGHTCAP were focused on furthering our understanding of the impact of melanopsin photoreception in neurophysiology and mapping the different brain regions directly or indirectly modulated by it. Several interesting findings and implications have been reached from these studies. In experiments by Qian Huang (ESR01), conducted with mice, it was found that the spatial distribution of light can modulate behaviour as much as overall scene brightness. Especially radiance differences around the horizon appear to be of relevance. This pattern distinction was found to be modulated through a melanopsin dependent pathway (ESR01).

The effect of melanopic light reception through melanopsin retinal ganglion cells (mRGCs) in melatonin suppression has been well established. Owing to this it has been universally recommended that we exercise caution with electric light that we expose ourselves to, in particular limiting our exposure to blue light in the evenings and at night. While mRGCs have been well studied in regulating melatonin suppression there is growing evidence that cones might also be contributing to this effect, and this is being investigated by Fatemeh Fazlali (ESR05) on both healthy participants with normal colour vision and those with red-green colour blindness.

2.1.2 Attention and alertness

Various aspects of lighting have been extensively studied to assess the optimal conditions for improved attention and work conditions. The effect of light directionality on attention and subjective sleepiness is an additional factor to consider when designing lighting structures. In a study done by Nikodem Derengowski (ESR12) on students and working professionals, it was found that there was a slight improvement in reaction times and subjective sleepiness when they were

exposed to light originating from the upper part of the visual field compared to other directions, while maintaining homogenous vertical illuminance at eye level. The effect of lighting on alertness was also studied by Aysheh Alshdaifat (ESR10) and Nima Hafezparast Moadab (ESR11), in the context of travel in the evening with test subjects being exposed to different lighting conditions (melanopic equivalent daylight illuminance (mEDI) ranging from 0.5 lx to 98.8 lx). For mEDI of up to 10 lx there were no statistically significant effects: however, increasing the mEDI to 98.8 lx revealed a significant reduction in reaction time and subjective sleepiness. Results from two outdoor studies done by Richard Jedon (ESR09), that looked at pedestrians' alertness under different lighting uniformity conditions, showed that reactions were faster, response accuracy higher and subjective sleepiness lower in non-uniform lighting conditions than in the uniform one.

Next, we move onto the NIF impact of melanopsin photoreception in a study on humans that explored blue light impact on brain activity. Roya Sharifpour (ESR04) found that the effect of light wasn't just dependent on age when comparing young adults (19-30 years of age) vs. teenagers (15-18 years of age) but is also dependent on gender and the time of day. Brain regions were also targeted in a very dose-dependent manner, with lower levels of blue light affecting sub-cortical regions of the brain and increasing light dosage leading to cortical regions being affected as well. Elifnaz Geçer (ESR07) found that higher levels of blue light affected daytime cognition and attention by means of modulating the EEG alpha, theta and beta power. Effects on the EEG beta power, seen as the proxy for higher cognition, were observed early on within the first minutes of light exposure whereas modulation of alpha and theta powers, which are associated with attention, were taking place mainly around 10 minutes after the start of the exposure. Results of this study contributed to untangling the timewise components behind the mechanisms of NIF effects during daytime.

2.1.3 Cognition

Beyond attention, light effects on performance on several higher-order cognitive tasks were explored in LIGHTCAP studies. These included oddball (ESR07) and Go-NoGo (ESR12) tasks testing inhibition, N-back tasks (ESR03, ESR04, ESR12) and free recall tasks (ESR09) testing memory, and an emotional task pertaining to categorization of male and female verbalizations (discussed further in deliverable 1.4). In addition, in healthy and sick rodents, Ashwathi Prithviraj (ESR02) employed a novel object recognition task, a spatial task and spontaneous alternation tasks to test cognition and thus track the progression of Alzheimer's disease under two different lighting conditions (dim vs bright).

Strikingly, so far none of these tasks demonstrated significant performance effects, in spite of concomitant significant effects on brain correlates (fMRI, EEG, by Jose Fermin Balda Aizpurua (ESR03), ESR04, and ESR07) in several of these studies. Various reasons for the absence of such effects have been suggested, including relatively short exposure times, compensatory or motivational mechanisms, and the premature (i.e., pre-symptomatic) testing of the transgenic mice, but we do acknowledge that so far (again, work is still ongoing) these effects appear to be somewhat underwhelming.

2.2 Health and sleep

Beyond CAP, sleep, mood, and health have always been important themes in light-related research and even more so since the discovery of NIF pathways. Also in LIGHTCAP, investigations have centred on these topics.

The effect of light was, for instance, studied on Alzheimer diseased nocturnal mice (ESR02). In the context of this neurodegenerative disease, long-term bright daytime light exposure as compared to dim did not significantly change the progression of cognitive decline as indexed by cognitive behavioural metrics and circadian function of the pathology at a pre-symptomatic stage of the disease, but there was a slight trend of improvement in behavioural metrics under the bright condition which could possibly have been a bigger effect if tested during the symptomatic stage.

For patients, sleep and circadian rhythms are key factors of health. Indeed, dysregulation or absence of sleep in sleep disorders can lead to a myriad of daytime complaints like extreme tiredness or sleepiness with a variety of physical, cognitive and social consequences (Vaida Verhoef (ESR08)). Even a simple reduction by half of the sleep duration among healthy people can also lead to an increase of daytime sleepiness. It is noteworthy that in both populations such symptoms of daytime sleepiness vary throughout the day, differently both between and within individuals (ESR08).

With such daytime complaints and daytime variation, light has a great beneficial potential. For instance, in persons suffering from chronic sleep deprivation, individual light exposure patterns may relate to the time-of-day dependent variation and the severity of daytime complaints of different types (cognitive, physical, affective). This hypothesis is still to be tested (ongoing study by ESR08).

In a study performed in an elderly care facility, individual light exposure was mapped and related to sleep-wake patterns. Results suggest that the averaged light exposure received across daytime may potentially reduce the amount of time spent napping for non-demented elderly people (Megan Danell (ESR14)). The impact of individual light exposure patterns is also being investigated amongst shift workers in health care, whereby the amount of light exposure on the day before shift work may mitigate the strain of shift work on sleep, circadian rhythm and metabolic activity (and rhythm) (Steffen Hartmeyer (ESR13), under investigation). In a study in office workers during winter, more time spent at higher light levels in the 3h before sleep negatively affected subjective sleep quality (ESR13).

The importance of light for sleep was already marked amongst adolescents. A study performed during winter in a classroom at higher latitude showed that modulating the indoor light scenario to increase its melanopic output (to 300 lx mEDI) during class hours beneficially affected the sleep quality of highschoolers who habitually experience poor sleep (ESR13, unpublished). In a study in adolescents by Rafael Lazar (ESR06), a bright light intervention (2500 lx, 4.5 hours, 1400 lx mEDI) during the afternoon and early evening acutely reduced adolescents' reported sleepiness compared to dim light (6 lx). However, the bright light intervention did not alleviate the negative effects of the subsequent evening light exposure (130 lx, 4.5 hours, 80 lx mEDI). Contrary to the main hypothesis

of the study, this bright light intervention further decreased rather than increased the adolescents' melatonin levels, possibly due to the acute phase-delaying effects of bright light from afternoon to evening. This may suggest that exposure to bright light until early evening is too late for adolescents to have a beneficial effect on melatonin in the same night.

2.3 Safety

The third domain where LIGHTCAP also ventured beyond pure CAP was safety in dark urban conditions. In the projects relating to safety (ESR09, ESR10, ESR11), different aspects of safety were distinguished, including both subjective safety perceptions and performance measures relating to alertness, attentiveness and hazard detection which may ultimately determine objective safety. Also, this included perspectives on drivers as well as pedestrians. The very novel aspect of these studies was that they included NIF-effect contributions and NIF-related phenomena such as alertness, thus complementing the many reports on the role of visual effects in safety and safety perception. Studies of ESR11 and ESR10 report how mEDI levels are relevant for performance on alertness and hazard detection for both drivers and pedestrians, but not in the range of levels that would be realistic or even feasible in nighttime urban settings. The studies of ESR09 highlight an intriguing contrast between light's effects on perceived safety – along the expected direction of more light renders better safety - and those on alertness, which suggest that lower or non-uniform light conditions may result in higher attentiveness of pedestrians. Interestingly, the latter project also demonstrated how non light-related situational or contextual conditions that raise a person's anxiety or arousal level did directly translate into increased lighting needs. Again, these preliminary findings should be taken with caution, but do point to relevant research avenues and design efforts to develop light settings that are both attractive and induce feelings of safety, while at the same time supporting pedestrians' diligence while navigating nighttime urban areas.

3 Implications for design and research

3.1 General lighting design recommendations

Current lighting design recommendations and standards articulate the use of mEDI as the current metric to use (CIE, 2018). Recommendations for daytime, evening, and nighttime indoor light exposures are mEDI > 250 lx, < 10 lx, and < 1 lx respectively (Brown et al., 2022).

To achieve the recommendations for daytime light exposure, architectural designers are generally capable of designing well daylight spaces through the use of orientation, ceiling height, and window-to-wall ratio, amongst other design methods. However, despite providing ample daylight, this is only beneficial and effective for the health and well-being of the occupants if they utilise the room accordingly. Having designed for effective daylight availability, does not guarantee the occupants will use and behave in the space in a manner that is optimal for their individual light exposure (ESR13, ESR14, and Myrta Gkaintatzi Masouti (ESR15)). Therefore, the role and understanding of occupancy behaviour is key to determining how much light individuals will receive within a given space.

For new architectural design projects, while it's difficult to predict exactly how occupants will behave within the spaces, increasing daylight availability within constructed spaces enhances the opportunity for occupants to receive sufficient light levels at the right time of day. This can be achieved through shallow/narrow floor plans, larger window to wall ratios, higher ceiling planes, and daylighting from above. However, these design criteria should be considered with care, as too much daylight may result in visual discomfort and, in turn, pulling blinds and blocking out the daylight source. In addition, it is realistic to consider that the majority of the useable space is not necessarily located along the façade perimeter. Therefore, methods of bringing daylight deeper into a space are required in order to increase daylight levels for the health and well-being of building occupants.

Within existing built spaces, it is much more feasible to understand the behaviours of occupants for a given facility but more challenging to instigate physical changes to the building to provide higher daylight levels. By measuring horizontal and vertical light levels within a given space and monitoring behaviour, we can gain useful insights about whether occupants are likely to receive “higher” or “lower” light levels, but these remain quite limited in predicting whether occupants will ultimately receive a sufficient light dose. Personalized light exposure tracking with wearable sensors, despite its own limitations (discussed further in deliverable 1.4), provide the opportunity to gain a better understanding of the available light exposures within the given space, how much is effectively experienced by its occupants, or where behaviour can be steered to improve light hygiene; together, this allows researchers and lighting designers to examine where more light is needed (ESR13, ESR14).

To increase natural light exposure within an existing space, one can consider changing/altering the behaviour of the occupants to favour an increased occupation of perimeter spaces (e.g. through furniture and/or room re-design) or changing/altering the architecture itself (e.g. through a façade renovation or a new partitioning of spaces).

One can also aim to bring more light directly to the occupants using electric lighting. Electric lighting makes it possible to complement available daylight levels by pointedly increasing light levels at specific locations and/or times, which can be particularly effective in areas that the occupants are habitually occupying anyway. When designing for increased interior light exposure within an existing space, the positioning of the light source and the directionality of illumination shall thus be considered. In an experimental study, luminaires placed above occupants (fixed on the ceiling or as pendent luminaires) were shown to slightly outperform luminaires placed on the side or directly in front of the residents in terms of alertness (ESR12). Given the fact that this effect was quite modest, positioning of the luminaire may not be as important as simply increasing the light levels in the places where residents spend their time.

When considering occupancy behaviour and the locations in which occupants inhabit, certain degrees of behaviour are more important than others. Considering the location of a person within the space and the direction in which residents are oriented in relation to the daylight opening(s) has a bigger impact than, for example, the gaze behaviour (ESR14, ESR15). Moreover, non-visual responses to light are modulated by continuous light exposure across timespans of hours, a day, or

several days. Hence, when designing for healthy lighting within a given space, the light exposure received by occupants outside of that space may play an important role in determining the impact of a certain lighting solution on general health and wellbeing (ESR13).

We refrain from lighting design recommendations for outdoor nighttime lighting in this document, as mEDI levels that seem to be relevant for driver and pedestrian alertness and hazard detection, are not realistic nor feasible in urban environments at night.

3.2 Implications for design tools

Architects and lighting designers need to have requirements and simulation tools, so that they can predict the effect of a certain lighting design on the CAP, health, sleep and safety of people (and animals). A survey (ESR15) demonstrated that many designers are hardly aware of the effect of light on CAP and don't use tools that could help them in the design. Therefore, we first need to define robust correlations between light and CAP, and figure out which lighting design aspects vary throughout time and, out of the factors that vary, which ones are most impactful. These insights should help to develop a more advanced simulation tool, that supports the design process of architects and lighting designers.

In real indoor and outdoor settings, the absolute amount of light and the spectral distribution that people were exposed to was found to vary greatly throughout the day and night, since people are exposed to different light sources (i.e., daylight and electric light of different types) (ESR13). In addition, under normal daily conditions within an urban environment, it was determined that spatial light distribution within a person's field-of-view (FOV) is highly variable depending on where a person is, what they are doing, where they are going, and how they get there (ESR13). With "spatial light distribution" we mean the light coming from the upper, lower, left and right parts of the FOV. Thus, if the design parameters (i) amount of light, (ii) spectral and (iii) spatial distribution are found to have a practically relevant effect on certain responses in lab and field studies, they should be considered in lighting design and the supporting design tools.

3.2.1 Amount of light

The impact of the amount of light during the day and night on cognition and alertness responses is partly known from literature (e.g., see Lok, Smolders, Beersma & de Kort, 2018; Souman, Tinga, te Pas, Van Ee & Vlaskamp, 2018) and this was further confirmed by lab and field experiments on humans and animals conducted within LIGHTCAP. During daytime, bright light (up to 190 lx mEDI) was found to modify brain activity over several regions (amygdala, hypothalamus, locus coeruleus (preliminary finding, ESR03, ESR04). Daytime bright light (175 lx mEDI) was further found to improve alertness by suppressing alpha power in comparison to dim light (2.5 lx mEDI) in healthy adults (ESR07). In a laboratory study that used mice models with Alzheimer's, daytime bright light levels (1800 lx mEDI) during the pre-symptomatic state were compared to dim light (18 lx mEDI). At this pre-symptomatic state, increasing daytime light did not significantly alter rest-activity rhythms or have a measurable impact on measures of cognitive ability. This study demonstrated a positive

trend, but the results were not statistically significant (ESR02). The amount of mEDI was found to predict steady-state pupil size in human subjects under real-life daylight conditions (ESR06).

We also learned that teenagers respond to light differently, which could be due to variations in their light sensitivity. Whether they are more or less sensitive compared to adults requires further research. On one hand, teenagers might be more sensitive to light due to developmental changes in the brain as well as in the eye, such as lens transparency and pupil size. On the other hand, they may be less sensitive because they spend more time outdoors or on multimedia screens. Despite these differences, adults still respond to light, and the potential negative effects of light on adults should not be overlooked in comparison to teenagers (ESR04). Age might not be the main driver of NIF impacts, but there are other parameters such as sex and seasonality that play a role (ESR05).

During the nighttime, mEDI was found to affect road user's alertness (measured by PVT performance and KSS) and drivers' cognitive performance. However, this was only the case under extreme light levels (100 lx mEDI for the pedestrian case and 80 lx mEDI for the driver case) that are unlikely to be used for outdoor nighttime lighting (ESR10 + ESR11). Interestingly, low light level and low uniformity at night at an outdoor light setting were found to decrease feelings of safety but improved alertness to an acoustic signal (ESR09).

3.2.2 Spectral distribution

Spectral power distribution of light was shown to have an impact on alertness and cognition during the day and at night by several LIGHTCAP projects. Yet, a laboratory experiment that implemented two light metamers of the same visual appearance but different melanopic contents could not replicate findings of experiments with monochromatic light on daytime alertness (measured with PVT, Oddball and KSS) (ESR07). Ongoing research will provide information on how cones and ipRGCs contribute to the modulation of alertness, cognition and brain function (ESR04, ESR05, ESR07). The potential involvement of multiple photoreceptors in NIF responses indicates that spectral content cannot be ignored in lighting design tools.

3.2.3 Spatial distribution

Findings on the effects of spatial light distribution are mixed. Vertical light distribution was shown to determine where the rodents spent their time, since mice demonstrated a preference for dark horizon (ESR01). Literature on humans shows that spatial light distribution is also important for humans during the nighttime (e.g. Glickman et al. 2003, Broszio et al. 2021). During the daytime, a light source positioned in the upper FOV was found to improve alertness compared to a light source positioned in the lower FOV (ESR12). The experiment's results were significant, but the effect size was very small, indicating that for practical applications in humans during the daytime, spatial patterns might not be the most important parameter to include in lighting design.

To summarise, including the amount and spectral content of the light in lighting design tools is necessary for an adequate simulation but also for the evaluation of a lighting design on an alpha-opic level. Including the spatial distribution, and distinguish in the evaluation whether the light comes from the upper, lower, left or right part of the FOV, is perhaps more relevant during the

night than during the day, and complicating design tools by considering this aspect is not required for daytime analyses.

In terms of including the spectral content in simulation tools, a study that compared simulated mEDI with measured mEDI under indoor electric light conditions found that low spectral resolution (three spectral bands) was less accurate than high spectral resolution (nine spectral bands) (ESR15). This indicates that increased spectral resolution of simulation tools is useful.

Within LIGHTCAP we worked on further developing an open-access tool that assists architects and lighting designers to predict the amount of light, the spectral content and the spatial distribution of light (Lark Spectral Lighting 2.0 - ESR15). The tool allows for the simulation of the amount of daylight and electric light indoors with a nine-band spectral resolution over a period of time. A workflow for spatially weighted analysis makes it possible to account for the direction of light within the FOV. A few simplifications are made in the current version of the tool (e.g. the assumption that the spectral distribution of daylight can be represented by a constant spectrum), thus future improvements might be necessary.

In addition to the lighting parameters, and as mentioned before, the behaviour of occupants in terms of (i) movement within a space and (ii) change of gaze might have an effect on the occupants' personal light dose and therefore might need to be included in design tools. A literature review demonstrated that these two behavioural aspects are rarely investigated (ESR15). Within LIGHTCAP the movement behaviour of residents in an elderly care facility was investigated as well as the gaze behaviour of office workers in a single person office (ESR14, ESR15 respectively). In both cases, the movement or gaze behaviour were not the most important aspects in determining personal light dose, but ongoing research will provide more information in the future. This indicates that complicating design tools by considering these aspects might not be of high priority and measuring or simulating light vertically at eye level might be sufficient, at least based on the current findings. More research is needed given the limited information that is currently available.

3.3 Implications for research

Research on the effects of light on cognition and perception relies on understanding both the characteristics and metrics of light, characteristics and metrics of human responses, and learning how parameters of the first category impacts those in the second. Across the experiments and field studies performed in this consortium, we have gained knowledge of the indicators and methods commonly used in light research, their advantages, and pitfalls. With these insights, we formulate implications for future research. The implications relate to two areas in particular:

3.3.1 Quantification of light exposure

Despite clear recommendations from the CIE on how to report light exposure characteristics in controlled laboratory settings, researchers still face a lack of consensus on how to best quantify the light. This is even more so in field applications where light remains mostly natural, and thus highly variable in intensity, spectral and spatial distribution (ESR13). Knowledge from this consortium on

the inter-individual variability in (natural) light patterns could guide future research into the development of reliable metrics. In turn, it will enable us not only to delineate a finer spatially-temporally-spectrally dependent dose-response relation between light and its effect but also to understand how to accurately simulate and conceptualise light in spaces and designs.

Our own studies (ESR06, in preparation) also suggest that light history plays an important role. While a recent history of bright light in the afternoon and evening (2500 lx, 4.5 hours, 1400 lx mEDI) decreased melatonin levels in adolescents later in the evening, bright light exposure (>1000 lx) recorded outside the laboratory during the ~32 h prior to each experiment was associated with increased evening melatonin and sleepiness. This may suggest that the beneficial effects of the (non-visual) adaptation to bright light may take longer than 4-5 hours in the afternoon and evening to manifest in adolescents. This in return also suggests that a single hour of dim light adaptation, as used in many studies, may not be enough to completely control and quantify light history in highly controlled experimental studies.

3.3.2 Operationalisation of the effects

Responses to light can be measured through a multitude of proxies. Across all projects, effects of light were investigated on subjective measures, cognitive behavioural metrics, and/or physiological outputs, most used in prior research, although new measures were also developed (e.g. see ESR01, ESR09). Each metric presents itself with challenges, particularly in terms of reliable interpretation or application to real-life situations. Investigations on common sleepiness scales (used in lighting research) and on the daytime complaints of patients with sleep disorders highlighted a mismatch between patients' experiences and what is measured by the scales (i.e. the Karolinska sleepiness scale, the Stanford sleepiness scale or the Epworth sleepiness scale) (ESR08). These observations put into perspective prior studies investigating effects of light on healthy participants using these scales and measures, and question how they can be generalized to clinical applications or even just other populations. The assessment and identification of key metrics based on lived experiences using qualitative research, as done by ESR08, can be informative to verify or improve the mapping of experiences or behaviours to measurements with instruments used in study designs for subsequent quantitative assessment.

In a similar fashion, research on humans (particularly on the effect of outdoor night light on pedestrians) and Alzheimer mouse models question the reliability and the relevance of behavioural markers, especially in reference to psychological concepts (like safety, alertness, or arousal, see ESR09) or to cognitive processes (ESR02). As a side note, genetic drifting needs to be considered when using a transgenic (e.g., Alzheimer) mouse model. Pathology development and timeframe are very important when studying potential therapies in Alzheimer Disease. But we also noted subtle differences in the application of task-based measures, such as the PVT. For instance, varying outcomes suggest that the duration of the PVT task matters to detect changes in attention and performance: 5 mins may not always suffice.

There is also no clear consensus on physiological measures like EEG frequencies. In particular, what the modulation of EEG frequencies means in terms of increasing attention or alertness, and which other EEG indicators can be used as alternative objective markers that relate to cognition,

attentional processes or alertness (ESR07). With the reflections gathered from all of these metrics, future research should further explore and improve the indicators we currently use to explore the effects of light.

4 Open questions

If we consider all the results presented (and under development) and their shortcomings, the following major challenges for further research arise:

4.1 Variability

We need to understand what underlies the variability in non-image forming light sensitivity across the human population. We need much more data relating light exposure to NIF responses in the real world so that we can establish when lighting is a concern (and when it isn't). Therefore, it would be necessary to perform large-scale (perhaps multi-centre) studies to quantify the effects of light and their dependencies, like age and gender, but also time of day, in a reliable, robust, and systematic manner.

4.2 Field studies

One big question relates to the applicability of the laboratory results in practice: What remains of the positive NIF effects found in the laboratory in the field under the same conditions? To verify the recommendations for NIF effects (as for instance formulated in Brown et al., 2022) we must therefore thoroughly investigate luminous exposure patterns in the field, the most important determinants of these patterns, and the effects of these exposure patterns in the natural context of daily life. This immediately implies the need to explore how we can meaningfully quantify light exposure: yes, we can collect realistic exposure patterns with novel dosimetry devices, but then what? Do we average over the hour? Over the day? Do we weight exposures higher at certain times of the (internal) day, or rather when it is dynamic and not constant? It may be necessary to adjust the level of detail to focus on particularly relevant aspects.

Another big challenge in the context of field studies is to figure out when light exposure becomes critical in real life. We know that aberrant light-dark schedules are unhealthy and that a strong day-night contrast is healthy, but when - at what levels, at what time, after how long - do these effects become measurable and significant enough that we should actively intervene or take them into account?

We would like to emphasize that participants should be recruited from a wide range of settings and population groups (e.g., including citizens with low socioeconomic status, clinical populations, etc.). In addition, standard working protocols for on-site assessments need to be developed specifically for field studies. In this, it is worth nothing, that our own studies indicate that age effects, the dose-

response relationship between pupil size and light intensity, and the superiority of melanopsin-weighted measures over photopic illuminance for predicting steady-state pupil size apply not only to lab- but also real-world conditions, but much more research is needed.

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